

Herbal Anti-Acne Face Wash: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Acne vulgaris is a common chronic inflammatory skin disorder affecting approximately 80-90% of adolescent and many adults worldwide. It is characterized by the formation of comedones, papules, pustules, nodules, and cysts, primarily on the face, chest, and back. Conventional anti-acne treatments such as antibiotics, retinoids, and benzoyl peroxide are effective but may produce adverse effects including skin irritation, dryness, and antibiotic resistance. Herbal cosmetics have emerged as a promising alternative due to their safety, efficacy, and minimal side effects. Herbal anti-acne face washes contain plant-derived ingredients possessing anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound healing properties. This review discusses the pathophysiology of acne, commonly used herbal ingredients, formulation aspects, evaluation parameters, advantages, limitations and future prospects of herbal anti-acne face washes.

Keywords: Acne vulgaris, Herbal cosmetics, Neem, Alove-vera, Turmeric, Tea tree oil, face wash.

INTRODUCTION

The skin is the largest organ of the human body and acts as a protective barrier against environmental hazards. Acne vulgaris is one of the most prevalent dermatological disorder, especially among adolescents and young adults. The condition develops due to excessive sebum production, follicular hyperkeratinization, bacterial colonization, and inflammation.

In recent years there has been growing interest in herbal cosmetic products because of consumer preferences for natural ingredients. Herbal anti-acne face washes are formulated using medicinal plants that possess anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and skin-soothing properties. These formulations provide effective acne management while minimizing adverse effects associated with synthetic chemicals.

2. OBJECTIVE

1. To understand the causes and pathophysiology of acne vulgaris.

2. To review medicinal plants used in anti-acne face wash formulations.
3. To highlight the advantages and limitations of herbal cosmetics.
4. To discuss formulation methods and evaluation parameters.
5. To identify future prospects for herbal anti-acne products

3. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF ACNE

3.1 Increased sebum production

Androgen hormones stimulate sebaceous glands, leading to excessive oil secretion.

3.2 Follicular hyperkeratinization

Dead skin cells accumulate within hair follicles, causing blockage, and formation of comedones.

3.3 Bacterial colonization

Cutibacterial acnes proliferates within blocked follicles and contributes to inflammation.

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3.4 Inflammatory Response

Bacterial growth triggers immune responses resulting in redness, swelling, and pustule formation

4. HERBAL INGREDIENTS USED IN ANTI-ACNE FACE WASH

4.1 Neem

Biological name - *Azadirachta indica*

Family - *Meliaceae*

Properties

Antibacterial, Anti- inflammatory

Antifungal, Antioxidant

Role in Acne treatment:

Neem inhibits acne- causing Microorganisms and reduces inflammation.

4.2 Turmeric

Biological name - *curcuma longa*

Family - *zingiberaceae*

Active constituent: curcumin

Properties

Anti- inflammatory

Antioxidant

Anti- microbial

Role in Acne treatment:

Reduces redness, swelling, and post acne pigmentation.

4.3 Aloe vera

Biological name - *Aloevera*

Family - *Asphodelaceae*

Properties

Moisturizing

Wound healing

Anti- inflammatory

Role in Acne treatment

Soothes irritated skin and accelerates healing.

4.4 Tea tree oil

Biological name - *Melaleuca alternifolia*

Properties

Broad spectrum antimicrobial activity

Anti-inflammatory effect

Role in Acne treatment:

Reduces bacterial growth and acne lesions.

4.5 Tulsi

Biological name - *Ocimum sanctum*

Family - *Lamiaceae*

Properties

Antibacterial

Antioxidant

Anti-inflammatory

Role in Acne treatment:

Control bacterial infection and improves skin health.

5. FORMULATION OF ANTI- ACNE FACE WASH

Ingredients	Function
Neem extract	Antibacterial agent
Termeric extract	Anti- inflammatory agent
Aloe Vera gel	Moisturizer
Tea tree oil	Antimicrobial agents
Carbapol 940	Geling agent
Glycerin	Humectant
Purified water	Vehicle

Method of Preparation

1. Disperse Carbopol 940 in purified water with continuous stirring.
2. Add glycerin and mix thoroughly.
3. Incorporate neem extract, turmeric extract, and aloe vera gel into the base.
4. Add tea tree oil slowly with constant stirring.
5. Adjust the pH to 5.5–6.5 using triethanolamine.
6. Make up the final volume with purified water.
7. Transfer the prepared face wash into suitable containers.

6. EVALUATION PARAMETERS

6.1 Physical Appearance

The formulation is evaluated for color, odor, consistency, and homogeneity.

6.2 pH Determination

The pH should be within the skin-friendly range (5.5–6.5).

6.3 Viscosity

Measured using a viscometer to ensure appropriate consistency.

6.4 Foamability

Determines the cleansing efficiency and consumer acceptability.

6.5 Spreadability

Assesses ease of application on the skin.

6.6 Stability Study

The formulation is stored under different temperature conditions to evaluate physical and chemical stability.

6.7 Skin Irritation Test

Performed to ensure the safety of the formulation.

7. ADVANTAGES OF HERBAL ANTI- ACNE FACE WASH

1. Contains natural and biodegradable ingredients.
2. Lower risk of skin irritation and adverse effects.
3. Possesses antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties.
4. Suitable for long-term use.
5. Environmentally friendly and consumer preferred.

8. LIMITATIONS

1. Variability in herbal raw materials.
2. Limited shelf life compared to synthetic products.
3. Possible microbial contamination if preservatives are inadequate.
4. Lack of standardization in some herbal formulations.

9. FUTURE PROSPECTS

The demand for herbal cosmetics is increasing globally. Advances in phytochemical research, nanotechnology, and standardized herbal extracts can improve the efficacy and stability of herbal anti-acne face washes. Future studies should focus on clinical evaluation, quality control, and large-scale commercialization of herbal formulations.

CONCLUSION

Herbal anti-acne face washes represent a promising alternative to conventional acne treatments. Medicinal plants such as neem, turmeric, aloe vera, tea tree oil, and tulsi possess significant antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound-healing properties that help manage acne effectively. These formulations provide safer and more sustainable skincare options with fewer side effects. Continued research and standardization will further enhance their therapeutic potential and consumer acceptance.

REFERENCES

1. Kligman AM. An overview of acne. *Journal of Investigative Dermatology*. 1974;62(3):268–287.

2. Draelos ZD. *Cosmetics and Dermatologic Problems and Solutions*. CRC Press; 2011.
3. Bhatia N, Sharma PC. Herbal remedies for acne vulgaris. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*. 2013;21(2):1–6.
4. Biswas K, Chattopadhyay I, Banerjee RK, Bandyopadhyay U. Biological activities and medicinal properties of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*). *Current Science*. 2002;82(11):1336–1345.
5. Gupta SC, Patchva S, Aggarwal BB. Therapeutic roles of curcumin. *AAPS Journal*. 2013;15(1):195–218.
6. Surjushe A, Vasani R, Saple DG. Aloe vera: A short review. *Indian Journal of Dermatology*. 2008;53(4):163–166.
7. Carson CF, Hammer KA, Riley TV. Tea tree oil: Antimicrobial and other medicinal properties. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*. 2006;19(1):50–62.
8. Pandey G, Madhuri S. Medicinal uses of *Ocimum sanctum* (Tulsi). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*. 2010;5(1):61–66.
9. Thiboutot D, Gollnick H, Bettoli V, et al. New insights into the management of acne: An update from the Global Alliance to Improve Outcomes in Acne Group. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*. 2009;60(5):S1–S50.
10. Zaenglein A L, Pathy AL, Schlosser BJ, et al. Guidelines of care for the management of acne vulgaris. *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*. 2016;74(5):945–973.
11. Mukherjee P K. *Quality Control of Herbal Drugs: An Approach to Evaluation of Botanicals*. Business Horizons Publishers; 2019.
12. Ali B, Al-Wabel NA, Shams S, et al. Essential oils used in aromatherapy: A systemic review. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*. 2015;5(8):601–611.
13. Hammer K A, Carson CF, Riley TV. Antimicrobial activity of essential oils and other plant extracts. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*. 1999;86(6):985–990.
14. Benson H A E. *Skin structure, function, and permeation. Topical and Transdermal Drug Delivery*. Wiley; 2012.
15. Kaur C D, Saraf S. Herbal formulations and their evaluation methods in cosmetics. *Indian Journal of Natural Products and Resources*. 2011;2(4):402–406.
16. Chanchal D, Swarnlata S. Novel approaches in herbal cosmetics. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*. 2008;7(2):89–95.
17. Bisset N G. *Herbal Drugs and Phytopharmaceuticals*. CRC Press; 2001.
18. Pandey M M, Rastogi S, Rawat AKS. Indian traditional Ayurvedic system of medicine and nutritional supplementation. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2013;2013:376327.
19. Verallo-Rowell V M, Dillague KM, Syah-Tjundawan BS. Novel antibacterial and emollient effects of virgin coconut oil in skin disorders. *Dermatitis*. 2008;19(6):308–315.
20. Dureja H, Kaushik D, Gupta M, Kumar V, Lather V. Cosmeceuticals: An emerging concept. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*. 2005;37(3):155–159.

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